

Warning: Activity deletion in progress! Some grades are about to be removed.

GN

GANESH NALE

Grade item	Calculated weight	Grade	Range	Percentage	Feedback	Contribution to course total
छत्रपती शिवाजी महाराज: जीवन व कार्य (Chhatrapati Shivaji Maharaj: Jeevan va Kaarya)						
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> QUIZ स्वाध्याय १	23.81 %	✓ 24.00	0-25	96.00 %		22.86 %
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> QUIZ स्वाध्याय २	23.81 %	✓ 18.00	0-25	72.00 %		17.14 %
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> QUIZ स्वाध्याय ३	28.57 %	✓ 26.00	0-30	86.67 %		24.76 %
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> QUIZ स्वाध्याय ४	23.81 %	✓ 20.00	0-25	80.00 %		19.05 %
AGGREGATION						
Σ Course total	-	88.00	0-105	83.81 %		-

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